

Beyond the Commute: Temporal Ridership Patterns and Socioeconomic Stratification in London’s Underground Stations

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Summary

Transport planning remains predominantly oriented toward peak-hour commuting, systematically disadvantaging workers with non-standard schedules. This study integrates temporal ridership patterns with comprehensive neighbourhood contextual data across London Underground stations. Applying Gaussian Mixture Model clustering to high temporal resolution smartcard data from 267 stations, we identify eight distinct functional types. Results reveal classical concentric organisation with substantial internal complexity. Working-Class Commuter Zones at intermediate distances exhibit compounded disadvantages: highest deprivation (20.71%), 90-minute earlier morning departures, unique Saturday work peaks, and forced car dependence despite economic constraints. Friday patterns reveal work flexibility inequalities, with Central Business District showing 26.9% peak reduction versus only 17.5% in Working-Class Commuter Zones. Two clusters extending beyond traditional hours highlight systematic disadvantage for shift-based workers. Findings suggest needs-based rather than distance-based fare frameworks may better serve equity objectives.

KEYWORDS: travel behaviour transport inequalities automatic fare collection data gaussian mixture model.

1 Introduction

Understanding how different population groups use public transport is essential for equitable service provision (Lucas, 2012; Church et al., 2000). Transport planning has traditionally focused on peak-hour commuting, overlooking behaviours of those with non-standard work schedules or non-employment travel purposes (Shaw, 2022; Mavrogeni et al., 2025; Sánchez de Madariaga and Zucchini, 2019). This oversight has important equity implications, as non-standard schedules disproportionately affect lower-income service sector workers.

Automated fare collection (AFC) systems enable unprecedented spatial and temporal analysis of public transport usage (Cheon et al., 2019; Bieler et al., 2022). Previous London Underground stud-

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ies demonstrated systematic spatial organisation with employment-oriented stations concentrated centrally and residential stations peripherally (Verma et al., 2021; Reades et al., 2016). However, these studies provide limited insight into neighbourhood socioeconomic characteristics and often exclude weekend patterns that reveal work schedule inequalities.

This study integrates temporal ridership patterns across weekdays and weekends with comprehensive neighbourhood-level data encompassing demographics, socioeconomic conditions, employment composition, and urban form, revealing how transport systems serve diverse populations beyond peak-hour commuters.

2 Data and Methods

Our study uses London Underground station entries and exits from Transport for London’s NUM-BAT 2024 dataset, derived from smartcard tap-in and tap-out records collected during a typical autumn week. Raw records are aggregated into 96 15-minute intervals throughout each day across four day types: weekdays (average of Monday and Tuesday-Wednesday-Thursday), Friday, Saturday, and Sunday. This temporal resolution aligns with established findings that mobility patterns stabilise at the 15-minute threshold (Zhong et al., 2016). We converted absolute counts into proportions representing each station’s share of daily activity within each interval, normalising temporal patterns across stations of different sizes. After removing stations with zero activity or variance, the final dataset comprised 267 stations, each with 768 features (96 intervals \times 2 types \times 4 day types).

We compiled neighbourhood context variables from five thematic categories: demographic factors (age distribution, household composition, ethnic diversity); socioeconomic factors (deprivation, car ownership, educational attainment, overcrowding); employment composition from Business Register and Employment Survey (accommodation/food, education, information/communication, manufacturing, professional/scientific, retail, wholesale); urban morphology (spatial signatures classification); and amenity provision (total count and diversity). For each station, the catchment area comprises all LSOAs intersecting an 800-metre buffer, representing typical walking distance (approximately 15 minutes). Continuous variables were aggregated by calculating means across LSOAs within catchments.

Using Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), we identified stations with similar temporal patterns. GMMs are probabilistic clustering methods that model data as arising from a mixture of multivariate Gaussian distributions, offering advantages over deterministic methods like k-means by accommodating flexible cluster geometries through covariance structures. We tested multiple combinations of number of clusters $k \in \{2, \dots, 14\}$ and covariance parametrisations (full, tied, diagonal, spherical), selecting the optimal model based on Bayesian Information Criterion. To assess whether contextual factors differ significantly across network averages, we employed one-sample t-tests for each variable within each cluster, examining relationships through hierarchical clustering of standardised contextual characteristics.

3 Results

3.1 Spatial Distribution

The GMM identified eight distinct clusters with clear concentric spatial distribution (Figure 1). Inner London is dominated by Central Business District, Entertainment Hubs, and Hybrid Residential-Employment Zone. Inner Residential extends predominantly north and south. Working-Class Commuter Zones extend west and dominate East London, occupying intermediate positions between inner and outer areas. Outer Residential occupies outer peripheries, particularly north-west. Mixed-Use with Nightlife scatters across the city in areas known for nighttime entertainment. Airport Hub comprises only Heathrow Terminal stations, functioning as a peripheral employment centre.

3.2 Temporal Patterns

Each cluster exhibits characteristic temporal signatures revealing distinct functional roles (Figure 2). Central Business District displays inverse patterns to residential clusters: pronounced exit peaks at 09:00 and entry peaks at 17:00-18:00, with substantial Friday peak reduction (26.9%) indicating high uptake of remote work among professional workers. Working-Class Commuter Zones present entry peaks at 06:30-07:00—approximately 90 minutes earlier than other residential clusters—unique Saturday morning entry peaks absent in all other residential areas, and minimal Friday reduction (17.5%), suggesting limited access to flexible work arrangements.

Hybrid Residential-Employment Zone shows balanced bidirectional flows with sustained high activity throughout weekdays and weekends, reflecting mixed residential and employment functions serving young professionals. Entertainment Hubs uniquely exhibit higher weekend than weekday peaks with pronounced late-night entry peaks at 22:00, reflecting London’s nighttime economy and

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of station clusters across London

visitor attractions. Mixed-Use with Nightlife displays traditional commuter peaks plus distinctive late-night exit peaks at 23:00-01:00 on weekends, combining residential and entertainment functions. Airport Hub exhibits triple-peak pattern (07:00, 13:00, 17:00) with balanced bidirectional flows matching shift-based airport operations, and sharp nighttime activity decreases reflecting flight restrictions.

Figure 2: Ridership profiles by cluster. Each plot represents the average ridership pattern throughout each day type, for entries (blue) and exits (red). Lines represent the proportion of trips undertaken during each 96 15-minute slot of the day. Solid lines represent weekdays, dashed, dotted, and dash-dotted lines represent Friday, Saturday, and Sunday.

3.3 Contextual Characterisation

Hierarchical clustering of contextual attributes reveals three major groupings (Figure 3). Employment-oriented central clusters exhibit younger populations, fewer households with children, highest professional employment (16.58-17.55%), lowest car ownership (31.26-40.64%), extensive amenity provision, and elevated population density, reflecting dense urban centres oriented toward employment and consumption. Airport Hub stands alone with highest deprivation (23.85%), unemployment (4.75%), and lowest density (1,386 persons/km²), reflecting spatial disconnect between peripheral employment and residential development.

Residential clusters show complex, non-monotonic patterns. Inner Residential areas exhibit moderate characteristics with below-average deprivation (17.31%), suggesting gentrifying neighbourhoods. Working-Class Commuter Zones show highest disadvantage: deprivation (20.71%), overcrowding (15.27%), unemployment (4.10%), highest proportion with children (38.49%), yet paradoxically high car ownership (69.38%). Outer Residential shows lowest deprivation (13.04%), highest car ownership (80.01%), oldest population (18.13% aged 65+), suggesting affluent suburban families. Mixed-Use with Nightlife displays youngest population, highest Black ethnicity (15.79%), elevated deprivation (20.32%), and highest accommodation/food employment (11.93%).

Cluster Profiling Heatmap with Hierarchical Clustering

Figure 3: Contextual characterisation heatmap showing standardised values and significance levels (*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001)

4 Discussion

Results demonstrate persistence of classical concentric urban structure while revealing substantial complexity. Spatial organisation aligns with Burgess’s concentric zone model and Alonso’s bid-rent framework (Burgess, 2015; Alonso, 1964), yet non-monotonic distance-disadvantage relationships challenge simple gradients.

Working-Class Commuter Zones at intermediate distances face compounded disadvantages reflecting suburbanisation of poverty (Hochstenbach and Musterd, 2018; Bailey and Minton, 2018). These areas show highest deprivation (20.71%) yet paradoxically high car ownership (69.38%), suggesting forced dependence for families with complex activity chains despite economic constraints (Curl et al., 2018; Lucas, 2012). Early departures (06:30-07:00), 90 minutes earlier than other residential clusters, reflect spatial mismatch between affordable housing and employment.

Saturday morning peaks—absent in other residential clusters—suggest higher weekend work among lower-qualified workers (Craig and Brown, 2014), imposing temporal constraints particularly significant given highest proportion with children (38.49%). Minimal Friday reduction (17.5% vs. 26.9% in CBD) indicates limited remote work access (Adams-Prassl et al., 2022).

Two clusters extending beyond traditional hours highlight disadvantage for shift-based workers (Shaw, 2022; Mavrogeni et al., 2025). Mixed-Use with Nightlife combines residential and entertainment functions with elevated hospitality employment. Airport Hub demonstrates spatial disconnect where lower-paid workers commute from affordable areas to peripheral employment centres (Woodburn, 2017).

5 Conclusions

This study integrated temporal ridership patterns with neighbourhood contextual attributes to reveal eight distinct clusters among London Underground stations, demonstrating coexistence of classical concentric organisation with substantial complexity. Non-monotonic distance-disadvantage relationships, differential work flexibility access, and temporal patterns extending beyond traditional hours reveal systematic transport inequalities.

Results carry important planning implications. More deprived communities exhibit non-standard schedules, with early departures and Saturday morning peaks linked to service sector shifts. Friday patterns reveal remote work disparities, with less-deprived communities showing larger weekday-Friday gaps. Disadvantage concentration in intermediate zones suggests transport investment focused solely on central-peripheral connectivity may miss needs of households in areas neither well-served inner neighbourhoods nor affluent suburbs.

The non-monotonic distance-disadvantage relationship indicates proximity-based fares may inadequately reflect spatial need distribution. Working-Class Commuter Zones face forced car ownership, constrained employment options, weekend work requirements, and longer commutes despite intermediate location, suggesting needs-based rather than distance-based frameworks may better serve equity objectives.

Future research could integrate individual journey attributes, explore longitudinal changes including post-pandemic shifts, and examine nighttime worker challenges. Greater attention to off-peak patterns and inadequate service provision during non-traditional hours would inform more equitable planning serving diverse populations beyond conventional commuters.

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7 Biography

- Clara Peiret-García is a Research Fellow in Urban Analytics at UCL's Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA).
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